

undergo slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation. A positive shift of $\sim 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been observed in this mode of vibration which is in conformity with the observations of earlier workers^{1,6,17}.

The Zr=O double bond characteristic stretching frequency have been observed in all the complexes at $\sim 960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ modes have been assigned in the range $400\text{-}350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{6,12,18}

In $\text{ZrO}(\text{LNO})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, the very strong ν_3 band and a strong ν_4 band have appeared at $\sim 1082 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, for the perchlorate ion, indicating that the tetrahedral symmetry is maintained and the perchlorate ions are not bonded to the zirconium ion^{6,20}. In the thiocyanato complexes $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\delta(\text{NCS})$ frequencies observed at ~ 2045 , ~ 785 and $\sim 490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, support the N-bonding isothiocyanate ion²¹. The absence of the ν_3 band of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) around $\sim 1360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the occurrence of two strong bands at $\sim 1525 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in spectra of nitrate complexes of PyO and LNO suggest the coordination of nitrate in these complexes^{22,23}. The bidentate nature of nitrate groups are confirmed by the presence of bands at $\sim 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2), 800 cm^{-1} (ν_6) and 730 cm^{-1} (ν_3/ν_5).

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On the "Solvates" of Metal Acetates with Acetic Anhydride

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THE products obtained by a slow reaction of alkali acetates (M^+OAc^-) with acetic anhydride (Ac_2O) have been termed¹ as "solvates" (complexes) of M^+OAc^- with Ac_2O . We find² that the product of the Perkin reaction of PhCHO , Ac_2O and K^+OAc^- contains a byproduct acid salt, $\text{K}^+(\text{OAc}, \text{HOAc})^-$, which has been attributed to partial hydrolysis of Ac_2O and to a subsequent reaction of HOAc with K^+OAc^- . These two observations led us to repeat the synthesis of the "solvates" of Li, Na, K and NH_4 employing the reported¹ procedure and of the acid salts by a reaction of M^+OAc^- and HOAc in ethanol³. The observation was that for a given cation both reactions yielded the same product. Infrared spectral studies and hot stage microscopic examination of the products and the literature data⁴ (indexed in the Table) reveal that the products are invariably the acid salts even when procedure reported for the synthesis of the solvates¹ was adopted; 06° instead of 96° as the melting point for the Na-product in the original paper is understandably a lapse of proof reading.

Infrared spectra of the K^+ -products obtained from both the types of reactions, for example, are the same (see Figure). The ir spectra of all the products are ill defined which is indicative of the species being acid salts^{5,6}. An elaborated discussion provided by earlier authors¹ on the ir spectra,

TABLE—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SOME MOAc-Ac₂O PRODUCTS WHICH ARE INFACIT M(OAc, HOAc) ACID SALTS

Compound	Melting Point, °C			C and H percentage of solva'es ¹				C and H percentage calc. by us			
	as in ref. 1	as in litr ⁴	found by us	C		H		for MOAc-Ac ₂ O		for M(OAc, HOAc)	
				Calc	(found)	Calc	(found)	C	H	C	H
Li(OAc, HOAc)	105-7	—	106	36.08	(35.84)	4.49	(4.36)	42.86	6.36	38.09	5.56
Na(OAc, HOAc)	06	—	96	33.33	(33.16)	4.16	(4.02)	39.13	4.89	33.80	4.93
K(OAc, HOAc)	144	144	144	41.08	(40.92)	3.87	(3.64)	36.00	4.50	30.38	4.43
NH ₄ (OAc, HOAc)	66	66	65	34.12	(33.82)	6.16	(6.04)	40.22	7.26	35.01	8.03

Figure. IR spectra of the KOAc-products obtained from (A) the KOAc-Ac₂O system according to ref. 1 and (B) a KOAc-HOAc (1 : 1) reaction in ethanol.

which has been made in an attempt to authentify the products to be MOAc-Ac₂O complexes, is therefore an irrelevant exercise.

For all the four products in question, the "calculated" percentage of elements (see Table) reported by the earlier authors¹ is incorrect even with respect to MOAc-Ac₂O complexes as seen from the comparison of values we report in the Table. It is interestingly significant that their 'found' values have consistently tied up with these incorrectly calculated values and not with the correct values for M⁺(OAc, HOAc)⁻ or MOAc-Ac₂O species that now we are showing in the Table.

The M⁺OAc⁻ salts of Li⁺ and Na⁺ exist as hydrated whereas those of K⁺ and NH₄⁺ are hygroscopic. The authors do not mention about the precautions they took to avoid the involvement of this water during 24 hours of the reaction between MOAc and Ac₂O they carried out¹. This suggests that during "solvate formation" Ac₂O gets hydrolysed to produce HOAc and the latter interacts with M⁺OAc⁻ to produce M(OAc, HOAc) as we found in the present work under controlled conditions in ethanol medium.

We were interested only in the study of the concerned four cations for all of which M(OAc, HOAc) salts instead of MOAc-Ac₂O solvates have been found to form. Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ should be rather more prone to the formation of M(OAc, HOAc) salts because in the presence of these low charge density cations the AcO⁻...HOAc conjugation is expected to be even more facilitated⁷. Therefore, there is no surprise if similar error of inference is made in the case of other products reported in the paper in question.

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Paper Chromatographic Studies of Inorganic Ions on Impregnated Paper : Separation of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

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MIGRATION of ions on papers impregnated with 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide has been studied.

Experimental

Paper strips were first soaked in a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 5.0 and dried. The papers were then uniformly sprayed with a 2% solution of PTT in acetone. They were dried in an inert atmosphere at room temperature and stored neatly. Spotting of the metal ions was done by a